

BARRIER EFFECT IN DIELECTRIC MATERIALS

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Abstract

The barrier effect in an electrical breakdown of condensed dielectrics is interpreted in the context of the mechanism of cascade interatomic Auger transitions in the insulator valence band. The necessary and sufficient condition of the barrier effect emergence is the presence of a layer of a disordered material. The space charge and current generation in the electrical breakdown channel was calculated in a polyethylene sample. The optimum spatial position of the barrier was shown to correspond to the minimum of the sum of electric field strength functions of the external and space charges in the sample.

Keywords: barrier effect in dielectrics, electrical breakdown of inhomogeneous dielectrics

Introduction

The barrier effect in high-voltage equipment is understood to be an increase in the breakdown voltage or breakdown time of insulation gaps due to using additional insulation layers placed in the main dielectric. The effect was discovered in the 1930's by E. Marx and H. Rozer, when studying discharges in air gaps [1, 2]. The barrier effect is widely used in high-voltage structures to increase the breakdown voltage irrespective of the state of matter of the medium (gas, liquid or solid) and voltage type (direct, alternating or impulse).

The barrier effect properties in condensed dielectrics have been extensively studied [for instance, 3-10]. Just as in gas, this effect is more significant with an increase in the dielectric permittivity of the barrier layer relative to that of the main dielectric. This can be accounted for by the decrease in the electric field strength in the barrier layer. The barrier effect efficiency improves with an increase in the conductivity of the barrier layer relative to that of the main dielectric. This is attributed to the free charge motion and electric layer generation on the dielectric boundaries whose electric field is opposite to the external one. The typical relationship between the breakdown voltage U_b in the dielectric – barrier layer structure with a point-to-plane configuration of electrodes and the barrier position takes the form of a curve with a maximum. The maximum value of U_b corresponds to the case when the ratio of the distance between the barrier layer boundary and the high-voltage electrode (d_1) to the total insulation length (d) was $d_1/d = 0.25-0.3$. In the research [3], the highest value of U_b was observed in samples of glass and crystalline NaCl with a barrier polyethylene film at a constant voltage and positive polarity of the point electrode ($U_b = 1.2U_{b0}$, where U_{b0} is the breakdown voltage of the main material with a thickness d). The maximum hardening was achieved when using a barrier from a metallic foil ($U_b = 1.27 U_{b0}$). The authors adhere to the barrier effect model proposed by E. Marx and H. Rozer. It implies that an increase in the dielectric strength can be explained by the surface charge accumulation on the barrier layer boundary, which reduces the electric field strength in the point-barrier region. As reported [3], this assumption is supported by a decrease

in the barrier effect with a shorter time of voltage application.

Following the research into the barrier effect, the studies [4, 5] used a layer of proton-irradiated material as a barrier layer in the polymer samples of PMMA and PELD. The samples were irradiated from the side of the ground electrode to different depths by attenuating the particle energy with aluminum foil. In the region $0 < d_1 < d$, the dielectric strength of the sample E_b is lower than that of the non-irradiated material E_{b0} . The maximum value of E_b corresponds to the barrier layer boundary position at $d_1/d = 0.25-0.3$. Then, with a reduction in the barrier layer, the dielectric strength decreases, but remains higher than E_{b0} . The polymer molecule destruction is believed to be accompanied by an increase in the concentration of broken bonds in the side chains and the main chain, which leads to higher conductivity in the irradiated part of the sample.

The studies [6-8] focused on the impact of barriers and interfaces on the lifetime of epoxy samples, as well as the specific aspects of the electrical tree growth under the conditions of an inhomogeneous field and alternating polarity voltage. Mica, PETP film [6], glass fiber, mica powder tape and polyimide film [7] were selected as barrier materials. The authors [8] used standard samples of solid epoxy cubes and samples with interfaces. The interfaces were created using two methods. In the first case, an acrylic cube mold was placed on the solid epoxy layer with a thickness of approx. 1 mm. Liquid epoxy was poured into it and left to solidify. In the second case, an epoxy layer was applied using a spin coater. This resulted in a flat and uniform film with a thickness of 0.485 mm on the cube surface. The interfaces were near the flat electrode.

In the research [7, 8], the average electric field strength ($E_{mid} = U/d$) in the sample with a point-to-plane configuration of electrodes at a peak voltage U was quite low $\sim 8 \cdot 10^4$ V/cm. The electrical tree velocity did not exceed ~ 1.5 m/s. The dynamics of a breakdown channel formation was investigated using the images of samples recorded continuously [7] and with an interval of 1 min. [8].

According to [7], the electrical tree developed and reached the barrier boundary. After that, the branches

According to [13, 19, 20], the beginning of the formation of a breakdown channel in the near-surface metal-dielectric region is associated with the formation of C^{2+} ions with two holes in the sp^3 orbital due to the tunneling transition of electrons into the metal. The recombination of the hole is likely to involve a neighboring carbon atom and take place through an interatomic Auger transition of the electron from the sp^3 -orbital of the C^0 atom to C^{2+} , with subsequent generation of the Auger electron to the conduction band. The subsequent hole recombination on C^{2+} is conditioned by the interatomic Auger transition of the electron from the C^0 atom in the carbon atom chain of the polyethylene molecule. The Auger electron transition to the conduction band occurs, if the minimal energy gap between sp^3 -orbitals of C^{2+} and C^0 atoms in the electric field is not smaller than the band gap width of the polymer.

The electric field strength on the surface of the breakdown channel front was estimated in the papers [13, 16]. In alkali-halide crystals, the necessary band bends for Auger transitions are provided by the electric field of the space charge that includes a layer of doubly charged haloid ions and layers of singly charged haloid ions [13, 16].

A single cycle of the space charge motion can be divided into two successive stages. At the first stage, when the critical strength ($\sim 10^8$ V/cm) of the local electric field is reached, the hole decays due to the interatomic Auger transition of the electron from the neighboring carbon atom. An Auger electron is generated to the crystal conduction band. The conductive channel moves one interatomic spacing. At the second stage, electrons are drawn from the space charge area by the external electric field. This provides the critical field strength for the next cycle to occur. The cycle time Δt is given by

$$\Delta t = \tau_A + \tau_1, \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_A \sim 10^{-16}$ s is the time of Auger transition, τ_1 is the time taken to reach the critical field strength.

The discharge channel motion in polyethylene is generally connected with a straight-line transfer of the positive charge successively to the nearest carbon atoms and generation of Auger electrons to the conduction band. Some electrons recombine with holes with heat release. The energy released is spent on chemical bond disassociation and free macromolecules formation. The thermal pressure creates a hollow channel with a gas phase. When exposed to thermal collisions, macromolecules break up into ions [15].

The breakdown channel structure is formed by a set of single channels of the Auger transition, going in the same direction. It includes a positive space charge and a conductive channel with electron-hole plasma. The channel stretches from the positive electrode deep into the sample.

The barrier layer stops the breakdown channel motion (Fig. 1). The space charge is expected to

$$\epsilon\epsilon_0 \int_0^{x_2} \frac{\partial E_1}{\partial t} dx = \int_{x_1}^{x_1+\Delta x} G \Delta x dx - \sigma \int_0^{x_1} E_0 dx - \sigma \int_0^{x_1} E_1 dx - \epsilon\epsilon_0 \frac{x_1}{(x_2 - x_1)} \int_0^{x_1} \frac{\partial E_1}{\partial t} dx. \quad (10)$$

remain without a layer of doubly ionized carbon ions. The subsequent channel motion is possible when C^{2+} ions form beyond the disordered layer boundary. The process occurs due to the tunnel transition of electrons from the barrier layer to the main dielectric through the energy levels in the band gap of the disordered material.

It is interesting to estimate the electric field strength of the space charge on the surface of the conductive channel front.

The space charge formation on the conductive layer boundary at $x = x_1$ with the concentrations of free electrons n and immobile holes p is described by the continuity equation (2) and Poisson's equation (3)

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = G - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (en\mu E), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial x} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon\epsilon_0}, \quad (3)$$

where e and μ are the electric charge and electron mobility, $\rho = e(p - n)$ is the volume charge density; $E = E_0 + E_1$ is the total electric field strength, where E_0 and E_1 are the values of the strength of the external electric field and space charge, respectively; ϵ and ϵ_0 are the values of the dielectric permittivity of the sample and electric constant, respectively. G is the volume rate of the Auger electron charge generation in the space from x_1 to $x_1 + \Delta x$, where Δx is the atomic layer thickness in the crystal ($\sim 4 \text{ \AA}$). The Auger generation time is from t_k to $t_k + \tau_A$, where t_k is the time taken to reach the critical field strength.

The initial and boundary conditions of the problem will be as follows:

$$\text{at } t = 0, \text{ the field strength } E = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{at } x \geq x_1, \sigma = 0, \text{ denote } E_1 = E_s(t), \quad (5)$$

where $E_s(t)$ is the electric field strength beyond the space charge boundary x_1 , $\sigma = en\mu$ is the conductivity. After the transformations (2) and (3), we get

$$\epsilon\epsilon_0 \frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial x \partial t} = G - \sigma \frac{\partial E}{\partial x}. \quad (6)$$

The integration (6) on the x coordinate using the boundary condition (5) gives

$$\epsilon\epsilon_0 \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = G \Delta x - \sigma E_0 - \sigma E_1 + \epsilon\epsilon_0 \frac{\partial E_s}{\partial t}. \quad (7)$$

The short-circuiting condition takes the form (8)

$$\int_0^{x_2} E_1 dx = 0. \quad (8)$$

To a first approximation, the equation (8) can be written as

$$E_1 x_1 + E_s (x_2 - x_1) = 0. \quad (9)$$

To find E_1 in (7), we shall express E_s in terms of E_1 and integrate the equation (7) with respect to x from $x=0$ to x_2 .

Given the short-circuiting condition (8), we obtain

$$\frac{\partial E_1}{\partial t} + \frac{E_1}{\tau} = -\frac{E_0}{\tau} + \frac{G\Delta x^2}{\sigma x_1 \tau}, \quad (11)$$

where $\tau = \varepsilon\varepsilon_0 x_1 / \sigma(x_2 - x_1)$ is the circuit time constant. The solution to the equation (11) for E_1 is found to be

$$E_1 = -E_0 \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \right) + \frac{G\Delta x^2}{x_1 \sigma} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\tau_A}{\tau}\right) \right). \quad (12)$$

A decrease in the field strength of the positive space charge E_1 occurs as a result of the actuation of the Auger electron field. Without the Auger generation, the field strength E in the sample region $0 - x_1$ is given by

$$E = E_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right). \quad (13)$$

The conduction current density in the space $0 - x_1$ is defined as

$$i_1 = \sigma E = \sigma E_0 \exp(-t/\tau). \quad (14)$$

In the space $x_1 - x_2$, the field strength of the space charge E_s with regard to (9) is written as

$$E_s = \frac{E_0 x_1}{(x_2 - x_1)} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \right). \quad (15)$$

The space charge is formed within the time $t_0 \approx (2-3)\tau$. In a homogeneous field, the strength E_s increases superlinearly with an increase in the x_1 coordinate. At $x_1 = 0.5x_2$, E_s equals E_0 with a subsequent sharp rise at $x_1 > 0.7x_2$. The spatial structure of the electric field of the space charge E_1 at $x_1 \approx 0.5x_2$ and $t > \tau$ is shown in Fig.1. The positive space charge induces the corresponding charge with a negative sign in metal electrodes.

To estimate the charge Q_s , creating the field strength E_s , we will use the Ostrogradsky-Gauss theorem [23]. We shall plot a closed cylindrical surface with the bases S_1 in the cross-section, where E_s is zero (Fig. 1) and S_2 in the region $x_1 - x_2$. The whole electric flux exits the charged region in one direction through the surface S_2 . Therefore, according to the Ostrogradsky-Gauss law, for the surface area unit of the charged layer, the condition holds

$$\varepsilon\varepsilon_0 E_s = Q_s \left[\frac{k}{cm^2} \right]. \quad (16)$$

The displacement current density in the space $x_1 - x_2$ is defined as

$$i_s = \frac{\partial Q_s}{\partial t} = \sigma E_0 \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right). \quad (17)$$

The conduction current density (14) in the region $0 - x_1$ equals the displacement current density (17) in the region $\sigma = 0$. According to the equation (14), the amplitude of the pre-breakdown current is expected to be constant during the motion of the conduction channel. In polymers and liquid dielectrics, the exponential

growth of the pre-breakdown current is observed [24, 25]. The result of calculating the electric current under the fractal model of the breakdown channel formation is close to the experimental result, given the growth of conductivity due to the Joule energy release in the breakdown channel. [26].

The time taken to reach the critical field strength τ_1 in the equation (1) can be found from the relationship

$$\tau_1 = Q_A / i_1, \quad (18)$$

where Q_A - is the charge density of Auger electrons according to the equation (12)

$$Q_A = \varepsilon\varepsilon_0 \frac{G\Delta x^2}{x_1 \sigma} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\tau_A}{\tau}\right) \right).$$

Cycle time Δt is defined as

$$\Delta t = \tau_A + \frac{G\Delta x^2 \tau_m}{E_0 x_1 \sigma} \exp\left(\frac{t_0}{\tau}\right) \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\tau_A}{\tau}\right) \right) \quad (19)$$

where $\tau_m = \varepsilon\varepsilon_0/\sigma$ is the Maxwell relaxation time. The formula for Δt makes it possible to estimate the dependence of the channel velocity $v(x_1) \approx \Delta x/\Delta t$ on the field strength E , conductivity σ , and coordinate x_1 .

In the case of a heterogeneous field, the maximum field strength near the point E_m in the «hyperboloid of revolution – plane» electrode structure is given by [27]

$$E_m = \frac{2U}{r \ln \frac{4d}{r}}, \quad (20)$$

where r is the curvature radius of the electrode. The relationship between the electric field strength E_x and the x coordinate in the gap $0-x_2$ of the dielectric can be found from the equation [27]

$$E_x = E_m \frac{r}{r+x}. \quad (21)$$

The distribution of E_x is heterogeneous and follows the hyperbolic law (Fig.2). In the inhomogeneous field, there is a point x_{mid} in the interval $0 - x_2$, where $E_x(x_{mid})=E_{mid}$. It means that in the region from the point electrode to the position x_{mid} , the field strength is higher than E_{mid} , whereas in the region from x_{mid} to the flat electrode it is lower. The value of x_{mid} is approx $(0.25-0.3)x_2$.

Taking the calculations into account, the electric field on the space charge interface in the point-to-plane electrode structure is given by

$$E_{s1}(t) = E_m \frac{r \ln\left(\frac{r+x_1}{r}\right)}{(x_2-x_1)} \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau}\right) \right). \quad (22)$$

The calculated curves of the spatial distribution of the external field E_x/E_m , space charge field E_{s1}/E_m and total field E/E_m in the space $0-x_2$ of the sample at $r=50 \mu m$ are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig.2. Functions of the electric field strength distribution in the sample: 1 - E_x/E_m , 2 - E_{s1}/E_m , 3 - E/E_m

The charge field strength E_{s1}/E_m increases super-linearly in the space $0-x_2$. E_{s1}/E_m equals E_x/E_m at $x \approx 0.3x_2$. The minimum of the function E/E_m in the region $\sim 0.3x_2$ is in satisfactory agreement with the optimal position of the barrier observed in the experiment.

Conclusion

The necessary and sufficient condition of the barrier effect emergence is the presence of a layer of a disordered material. According to the concept of the mechanism of cascade interatomic Auger transitions, the delay in the movement of the breakdown channel at the boundary of the disordered layer is associated with the need to form a layer of doubly charged ions of the substance. An increase in the strength of the external field and space charge field, as well as the presence of conduction channels in the band gap of the defective layer contribute to the generation of such layer. This assumption is satisfactorily supported by the agreement between the experimentally obtained optimal position of the barrier and the calculated minimum of the sum of electric field strength functions of the external and space charges in the sample.

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